

SOLUTION OF FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION INVOLVING CERTAIN SPECIAL FUNCTIONS

S. Kumar¹, Owais Khan^{1*}, N.U. Khan²

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Integral University, Lucknow-226026, India

²Department of applied mathematics, faculty of Engineering and Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202002, India.

Abstract— The aim of the present paper is to compute the solution of fractional differential equation involving hypergeometric function and Laguerre polynomials. Moreover we find the fractional derivative formulas of hypergeometric function and Laguerre polynomials.

Keywords— Hypergeometric function, Laguerre Polynomials, Fractional derivatives,

I. INTRODUCTION

Fractional differential equations, which incorporate these derivatives and are used to explain a variety of physical phenomena, were developed as a result of the study of fractional derivatives. Innovation in science and technology is aided by fractional calculus, which offers a more flexible and sophisticated framework for the modelling and analysis of complex systems. When $f(x)$ is a function of order α , its fractional derivative is represented mathematically as $D^\alpha f(x)$, where α is a non-integer. Fractional derivatives are defined in various ways, with Riemann-Liouville, Caputo, and Grunwald-Letnikov derivatives being some of the more popular ones. Each has benefits and uses of its own. The fractional derivative of $f(x)$ in the Caputo sense is defined as

$$D^\alpha f(x) = I^{m-\alpha} D^m f(x) \quad (1.1)$$

$$D^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{m-\alpha-1} f^{(m)}(t) dt \quad (1.2)$$

For $m-1 < \alpha \leq m, m \in \mathbb{N}, x > 0$

For the Caputo derivative, we have $D^\alpha C = 0$, C is constant.

$$D^\alpha t^n = \begin{cases} 0, & n \leq \alpha - 1 \\ \frac{\Gamma(n-1)}{\Gamma(n-\alpha+1)} t^{n-\alpha}, & n > (\alpha - 1) \end{cases} \quad (1.3)$$

Special functions play a crucial role in various branches of Mathematics, Physics, Engineering and other scientific disciplines. These functions often arise when dealing with complex mathematical problems that cannot be expressed in term of elementary functions. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in extension, known as fractional calculus, has opened up new avenues for understanding and solving problems involving special functions. A class of functions known as fractional special functions has been developed and explored as a result of the relationship between fractional calculus and special functions. These functions are very useful in explaining complex systems and phenomena because of their distinctive characteristics and behaviors. The fractional derivatives of classical special functions like the Mittag-Leffler functions, Bessel functions and the Gamma function are a few well-known examples.

The hypergeometric series were studied by Leonhard Euler, but the first full systematic treatment was given by Carl Friedrich Gauss (1913). C.F. Gauss systematically formulated his famous infinite series as follows

$${}_2F_1(A, B; C; z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{z^n}{n!} \right) = 1 + \frac{ab}{c} \frac{z}{1!} + \frac{a(a+1)b(b+1)}{c(c+1)} \frac{z^2}{2!} + \dots, \quad (1.4)$$

where $(a)_n = a(a+1)(a+2) \dots (a+n-1)$; $(a)_0 = 1$

The series is of prime importance to mathematicians and reduces to the elementary geometric series. Hence it is called the hypergeometric series or, more precisely, Gauss's hypergeometric series and usually represented by the symbol ${}_2F_1(a, b; c; z)$, the well-known Gauss hypergeometric function. The series is not defined if c is zero or negative integer and terminates if either a and b are zero or negative integer.

The function ${}_2F_1(a, b; c; z)$ is a solution, regular at $z = 0$, of the hypergeometric differential equation

$$z(1-z) \frac{d^2 u}{dz^2} + [c - (a+b+1)z] \frac{du}{dz} - abu = 0,$$

Where a , b and c are independent of z . This is a homogeneous linear differential equation of the second order and at most three singularities 0 , ∞ and 1 which are all regular.

For $|z| < 1$ and $R(c) > R(b) > 0$, this function has the integral representation

$${}_2F_1(a, b; c; z) = \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \int_0^1 t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-b-1} (1-zt)^{-a} dt$$

The hypergeometric series converges for all z , real or complex, such that $|z| < 1$. Diverges for $|z| > 1$, and converges absolutely for $z = 1$ if $R(c - a - b) > 0$, and also when $z = -1$ if $R(c - a - b) > -1$.

The Generalized Hypergeometric Function: A natural generalization of the hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1$ is the generalized hypergeometric function, so called ${}_pF_q$ which is defined as

$${}_pF_q \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_p \\ b_1, \dots, b_q \end{matrix}; z \right] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1)_n \dots (a_p)_n z^n}{(b_1)_n \dots (b_q)_n n!} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{[(a)]_n z^n}{[(b)]_n n!},$$

where as usual

$$(a_i)_n = \frac{\Gamma(a_i + n)}{\Gamma(a_i)} \quad \text{and} \quad [(a)]_n = \prod_{i=1}^p (a_i)_n$$

Here p and q are positive integers or zero, the numerator parameters $a_1, \dots, a_p$ and the denominator parameters $b_1, \dots, b_q$ take on complex values, provided that $b_j \neq 0, -1, -2, \dots$; $j = 1, 2, \dots, q$.

Generalization of the generalized hypergeometric series ${}_pF_q$ is due to Fox and Wright [6] who studied the asymptotic expansion of the generalized hypergeometric function [6,p.21] defined by

$${}_p\Psi_q \left[\begin{matrix} (\alpha_1, A_1), \dots, (\alpha_p, A_p) \\ (\beta_1, B_1), \dots, (\beta_q, B_q) \end{matrix}; z \right] = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\prod_{j=1}^p \Gamma(\alpha_j + A_j k) z^k}{\prod_{j=1}^q \Gamma(\beta_j + B_j k) k!}$$

is known as generalized Wright hypergeometric function or Fox-Wright function where the coefficients $A_1, \dots, A_p$ and $B_1, \dots, B_q$ are positive real numbers such that

$$1 + \sum_{j=1}^q B_j - \sum_{j=1}^p A_j > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 0 < |z| < \infty; \quad z \neq 0$$

$$1 + \sum_{j=1}^q B_j - \sum_{j=1}^p A_j = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 0 < |z| < A_1^{-A_1} \dots A_p^{-A_p} B_1^{-B_1} \dots B_q^{-B_q}$$

A special case of Fox-Wright function is

$${}_p\Psi_q \left[\begin{matrix} (\alpha_1, 1), \dots, (\alpha_p, 1) \\ (\beta_1, 1), \dots, (\beta_q, 1) \end{matrix}; Z \right] = \frac{\prod_{j=1}^p \Gamma(\alpha_j)}{\prod_{j=1}^q \Gamma(\beta_j)} {}_pF_q \left[\begin{matrix} \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_p \\ \beta_1, \dots, \beta_q \end{matrix}; Z \right],$$

where ${}_pF_q$ is the generalized hypergeometric series.

The importance of Mittag-Leffler function and its generalization is realized during last one and half decades due to its direct involvement in the problem of physics, biology, engineering and applied sciences. Mittag-Leffler naturally occurs as the solution of fractional order differential equations and fractional order integral equation. The special function

$$E_\nu(z) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^r}{\Gamma(1 + \nu r)}, \quad (\nu, z \in R(\nu) > 0) \tag{1.5}$$

is called Mittag-Leffler function. The function $E_\alpha(z)$ was introduced by Gosta Mittag-Leffler [6], in connection with his method of summation of some divergent series, and its general form

$$E_{\eta,\nu}(z) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^r}{\Gamma(\eta + \nu r)}, \quad (\eta, z \in C; R(\eta) > 0, R(\nu) > 0) \tag{1.6}$$

II. FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVE FORMULAS

In this section we find the fractional derivatives formulas of hypergeometric function and Laguerre polynomials.

The term of hypergeometric function is decomposed by an infinite series of components:

$$y(x) = F(a, b, c; Ax^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(Ax^\alpha)^n}{n!} \right) \tag{2.1}$$

$$y(x) = 1 + \frac{ab}{c} \frac{z}{1!} + \frac{a(a+1)b(b+1)}{c(c+1)} \frac{z^2}{2!} + \dots \tag{2.2}$$

Then from (1.2) and (2.1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} D^\alpha y(x) &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{m-\alpha-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) D^m t^{n\alpha} dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{m-\alpha-1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(n\alpha-m+1)} t^{n\alpha-m} dt \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(n\alpha-m+1)} \int_0^x x^{m-\alpha-1} \left(1 - \frac{t}{x}\right)^{m-\alpha-1} t^{n\alpha-m} dt. \end{aligned}$$

Now let $\frac{t}{x} = u, dt = xdu$

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(n\alpha-m+1)} x^{\alpha(n-1)} \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha-m+1)\Gamma(m-\alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha(n-1)+1)}.$$

On solving we get the solution

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n (b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha(n-1)+1)} x^{\alpha(n-1)}. \tag{2.3}$$

Similarly we can find

$$D^{2\alpha}y(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n(b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(\alpha(n-2) + 1)} x^{\alpha(n-2)} \quad (2.4)$$

Again if Mittag-Leffler function suggest that the linear term $y(x)$ is decomposed by polynomial series of components

$$y(x) = E_v(Ax^\alpha) = \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(Ax^\alpha)^r}{\Gamma(1 + vr)}, \quad (v, z \in R(v) > 0) \quad (2.5)$$

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{m-\alpha-1} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^r}{\Gamma(1+vr)} D^m t^{r\alpha} dt$$

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{m-\alpha-1} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(r\alpha - m + 1)} t^{r\alpha - m} dt$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(r\alpha - m + 1)} \int_0^x (x-t)^{m-\alpha-1} t^{r\alpha - m} dt$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(r\alpha - m + 1)} \int_0^x x^{m-\alpha-1} \left(1 - \frac{t}{x}\right)^{m-\alpha-1} t^{r\alpha - m} dt$$

Now let $\frac{t}{x} = u$, and $dt = xdu$, above equation becomes

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(r\alpha - m + 1)} x^{m-\alpha-1+r\alpha-m+1} \int_0^x (1-u)^{m-\alpha-1} u^{r\alpha - m} du.$$

By using β function we get

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(r\alpha - m + 1)} x^{\alpha(r-1)} \frac{\Gamma(m-\alpha)\Gamma(r\alpha - m + 1)}{\Gamma(m-\alpha + r\alpha - m + 1)}$$

$$D^\alpha y(x) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(\alpha(r-1) + 1)} x^{\alpha(r-1)} \quad (2.6)$$

Similarly we can find

$$D^{2\alpha}y(x) = \sum_{r=2}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(\alpha(r-2) + 1)} x^{\alpha(r-2)} \quad (2.7)$$

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we consider few examples that demonstrate the Hypergeometric function and Mittag-Leffler function for solving linear differential equation with fractional derivatives.

Examples 1. The solution of following fractional differential equation

$$D^\alpha y(x) + By(x) = 0$$

By equation (3.1) and (3.3)

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n(b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) \frac{\Gamma(n\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(\alpha(n-1) + 1)} x^{\alpha(n-1)} - B \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n(b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(Ax^\alpha)^n}{n!} \right) = 0$$

Replace n by $n+1$ in first summation

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_{n+1}(b)_{n+1}}{(c)_{n+1}} \cdot \frac{(A)^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} \right) \frac{\Gamma((n+1)\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha n+1)} x^{\alpha n} - B \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n(b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(Ax^\alpha)^n}{n!} \right) = 0$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{(a)_n(b)_n}{(c)_n} \cdot \frac{(A)^n}{n!} \right) \left[\frac{(a+n)(b+n)}{(c+n)} \frac{A}{(n+1)} \frac{\Gamma((n+1)\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha n+1)} - B \right] x^{\alpha n} = 0$$

Now equating to zero the coefficient of $x^{n\alpha}$

$$\frac{(a+n)(b+n)}{(c+n)} \frac{A}{(n+1)} \frac{\Gamma((n+1)\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha n+1)} - B = 0$$

$$A(a+n)(b+n)\Gamma((n+1)\alpha+1) = B(c+n)(n+1)\Gamma(\alpha n+1)$$

at $n = 0, Aab\Gamma(\alpha+1) = Bc$

at $n = 1, A(a+1)(b+1)\Gamma(2\alpha+1) = 2B(c+1)\Gamma(2\alpha+1)$

at $n = 2, A(a+2)(b+2)\Gamma(3\alpha+1) = 3B(c+2)\Gamma(3\alpha+1)$

And so on. Now substituting these values in equation (2.2), we get

$$y(x) = 1 + B \frac{x^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + B^2 \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} + B^3 \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

Example 2. Consider the following fractional differential equation

$$D^\alpha y(x) - B'y(x) = 0.$$

By equation (2.5) & (2.6)

$$\sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{A^r \Gamma(r\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(\alpha(r-1)+1)} x^{\alpha(r-1)} - B' \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(Ax^\alpha)^r}{\Gamma(1+vr)} = 0.$$

Replace r by r+1 in first summation

$$\sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^{r+1} \Gamma((r+1)\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(1+v(r+1))\Gamma(\alpha r+1)} x^{\alpha r} - B' \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(Ax^\alpha)^r}{\Gamma(1+vr)} = 0$$

$$\sum_{r=0}^{\infty} A^r \left[A \frac{\Gamma(\alpha(r+1)+1)}{\Gamma(1+v(r+1))\Gamma(\alpha r+1)} - B' \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+vr)} \right] x^{\alpha r} = 0.$$

Now equating to zero the coefficient of $x^{\alpha r}$, we get

$$A \frac{\Gamma(\alpha(r+1)+1)}{\Gamma(1+v(r+1))\Gamma(\alpha r+1)} - B' \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+vr)} = 0$$

$$A = B' \frac{\Gamma(1+v(r+1))\Gamma(\alpha r+1)}{\Gamma(1+vr)\Gamma(\alpha(r+1)+1)}$$

at $r = 0, A = B' \frac{\Gamma(1+v)\Gamma(1+\alpha)}{\Gamma(1)\Gamma(\alpha+1)} = B' \frac{\Gamma(v+1)}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}$

at $r = 1, A^2 = B'^2 \frac{\Gamma(2v+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}$

at $r = 3, A^3 = B'^3 \frac{\Gamma(3v+1)}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)}$

And so on, now substituting the values of A, A^2, A^3 in equation (2.5)

$$y = 1 + B' \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha + B'^2 \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} x^{2\alpha} + B'^3 \frac{1}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} x^{3\alpha} + \dots (3.3).$$

Example 3. Again we take a fractional differential equation

$$D^{2\alpha} y(x) - Cy(x) = 0 \tag{3.4}$$

From (2.5) & (2.7) we get

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{a^k \Gamma(k\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta) \Gamma(\alpha(k - 2) + 1)} x^{\alpha(k-2)} - C \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^k x^{k\alpha}}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)} = 0.$$

Replacing k by k+2 in the above equation (only in left summation), then

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^k \Gamma(\alpha(k + 2) + 1)}{\Gamma(\eta(k + 2) + 1) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} x^{\alpha k} - C \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^k x^{k\alpha}}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)} = 0$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\frac{a^{k+2} \Gamma(\alpha(k + 2) + 1)}{\Gamma(\eta(k + 2) + 1) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} x^{\alpha k} + C \frac{a^k}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)} \right] x^{k\alpha} = 0.$$

An equating to zero the coefficient of $x^{\alpha k}$ in the above equation, we get

$$\frac{a^{k+2} \Gamma(\alpha(k + 2) + 1)}{\Gamma(\eta(k + 2) + 1) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} = C \frac{a^k}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)}$$

$$a^{k+2} = C a^k \frac{\Gamma(\eta(k + 2) + 1) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta) \Gamma(\alpha(k + 2) + 1)}$$

at $k = 0$, $a^2 = C \frac{\Gamma(2\eta + 1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha + 1)}$

at $k = 1$, $a^3 = C a \frac{\Gamma(3\eta + 1) \Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + \eta) \Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}$

at $k = 2$, $a^4 = C a^2 \frac{\Gamma(4\eta + 1) \Gamma(2\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + 2\eta) \Gamma(4\alpha + 1)} = C^2 \frac{\Gamma(4\eta + 1)}{\Gamma(4\alpha + 1)}$

at $k = 3$, $a^5 = C a^3 \frac{\Gamma(5\eta + 1) \Gamma(3\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + 3\eta) \Gamma(5\alpha + 1)} = C^2 a \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1) \Gamma(5\eta + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + \eta) \Gamma(5\alpha + 1)}$

Now put these values in equation (2.5) then,

$$y = 1 + A \frac{x^\alpha}{\Gamma(\eta + 1)} + A^2 \frac{x^{2\alpha}}{\Gamma(2\eta + 1)} + A^3 \frac{x^{3\alpha}}{\Gamma(3\eta + 1)} + A^4 \frac{x^{4\alpha}}{\Gamma(4\eta + 1)} + \dots$$

$$y = 1 + A \frac{x^\alpha}{\Gamma(\eta+1)} + C \frac{1}{\Gamma(2\eta+1)} x^{2\alpha} + CA \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(3\eta+1)} x^{3\alpha} + C^2 \frac{1}{\Gamma(4\eta+1)} x^{4\alpha} + \dots \quad (3.5).$$

Example 4. Again we take a fractional differential equation

$$D^{2\alpha} y(x) + D^\alpha y(x) - 2y(x) = 0 \tag{3.6}$$

Then by equation (2.5), (2.6) & (2.7),

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{a^k \Gamma(k\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta) \Gamma(\alpha(k - 2) + 1)} x^{\alpha(k-2)} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{a^k \Gamma(k\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta) \Gamma(\alpha(k - 1) + 1)} x^{\alpha(k-1)} - 2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^k x^{k\alpha}}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)} = 0$$

Replacing k by k+2 and k+1 in the first and second summation respectively,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^{k+2} \Gamma(\alpha(k + 2) + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + (k + 2)\eta) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} x^{\alpha k} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^{k+1} \Gamma(\alpha(k + 1) + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + (k + 1)\eta) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} x^{\alpha(k-1)} - 2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{a^k x^{k\alpha}}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)} = 0$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a^k x^{k\alpha} \left[\frac{a^2 \Gamma(\alpha(k + 2) + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + (k + 2)\eta) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} + \frac{a^1 \Gamma(\alpha(k + 1) + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + (k + 1)\eta) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} - \frac{2}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)} \right] = 0.$$

An equating to zero the coefficient of $x^{k\alpha}$

$$\frac{a^{k+2} \Gamma(\alpha(k + 2) + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + (k + 2)\eta) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} + \frac{a^{k+1} \Gamma(\alpha(k + 1) + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + (k + 1)\eta) \Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} - \frac{2a^k}{\Gamma(1 + k\eta)} = 0$$

at $k = 0$, $\frac{a^2 \Gamma(2\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + 2\eta)} + \frac{a^1 \Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{\Gamma(1 + \eta)} - \frac{2}{\Gamma(1)} = 0$

$$a^2 = \frac{2\Gamma(1+\eta)\Gamma(1+2\eta) - a\Gamma(\alpha+1)\Gamma(1+2\eta)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)\Gamma(1+\eta)}$$

$$\text{at } k = 1, \quad \frac{a^3\Gamma(3\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(1+3\eta)\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{a^2\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(1+2\eta)\Gamma(\alpha+1)} = \frac{2}{\Gamma(1+\eta)}$$

$$a^3 = a\Gamma(\alpha+1) \left[\frac{2\Gamma(1+3\eta)+1}{\Gamma(1+\eta)\Gamma(3\alpha+1)\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} - \frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} \right]$$

and so on now by equation (2.5)

$$y = 1 + ax^\alpha + \frac{a^2}{\Gamma(1+2\eta)}x^{2\alpha} + \frac{a^3}{\Gamma(1+3\eta)}x^{3\alpha} + \dots$$

$$y = 1 + ax^\alpha + \left[\frac{2}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} - a \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma(2\alpha+1)\Gamma(1+\eta)} \right] x^{2\alpha}$$

$$+ [a\Gamma(\alpha+1) \left[\frac{2}{\Gamma(1+\eta)\Gamma(3\alpha+1)} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+\eta)\Gamma(1+3\eta)\Gamma(3\alpha+1)\Gamma(2\alpha+1)} \right]$$

$$- \frac{2}{\Gamma(3\alpha+1)\Gamma(2\alpha+1)}] x^{3\alpha} + \dots \dots$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we found the solution of fractional differential equation of hypergeometric function and Laguerre polynomial. From the above result we conclude that we should compute the solution of fractional differential equation involving other special functions like as Mittag-Leffler function, Whittaker function, Bessel function, Hypergeometric polynomials, Jacobi polynomials, etc.

Acknowledgment: All authors would like to thanks Integral University, Lucknow, India for providing the manuscript (MCN): IU/ R&D/ 2024-MCN0002401 for this research work.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Erd'elyi, A. : Transformation of hypergeometric function of two variables, Proc. Roy. Soc. Edinburg A, 62 (1948), 378-385.
- [2] Kummer, E.E. : Uber die hypergeometrische Reihe " F(a; b; x), J. Reine Angew. Math. 15 (1836), 39-83.
- [3] Rainville, E.D. : Special Functions, The Macmillan Company, New York, 2013.
- [4] Romero, L., Cerutti, R., Luque, L., A new fractional Fourier transform and convolutions products, Int. J. Pure and Appl. Math. 66 (4) (2011), 397-408.
- [5] Saigo, M.: A remark on integral operators involving the Gauss hypergeometric functions, Math. Rep. Coll. Gen. Educ. Kyushu Univ. 11 (1978), 135-143.
- [6] Srivastava, H.M., Manocha, H.L. A Treatise on generating functions, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1984.
- [7] M. Kamarujjama, O. Khan, Computation of new class integrals involving generalized Galue type Struve function, J. Compute. Appl. Math. 351 (2019) 228-236.
- [8] Khan, N.U., Khan, M.I., Khan, O., Evaluation of Transforms and Fractional Calculus of New Extended Wright Function, Int. J. Appl. Comput. Math, 8:163, (2019), 1-5.
- [9] Khan, N.U., Khan, M.I., Khan, O., Certain finite integrals involving generalized Wright function, Advanced Mathematical Models & Applications, 6, (3), (2021), 292-301.
- [10] Khan, N.U., Husain, S., Khan, O., A novel kind of beta logarithmic function and their properties, Hacet. J. Math. Stat. 52 (4) (2023),945-955.
- [11] Khan, O., Kamarujjama, M., Khan, M.U., Baleanu, D., Nisar,K.S., Computational solution of fractional kinetic equations using Mathieutype series, Adv Differ Equ. 2019, 234 (2019)